

**Cognitive processing weakness among pupils in Demonstration Primary School, Federal
College of Education, Kano**

By

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Abstract

This study explored Cognitive Processing Weakness (CPW) among pupils in Demonstration Primary School, Federal College of Education (FCE), Kano. The purpose of the study was to find out whether weakness in pupils' cognitive processing differ among the six domains. Descriptive survey design was employed in which Two Hundred and Thirty Four (234) pupils were proportionately sampled from a population of 644 school children. Cognitive Processing Inventory (CPI), a standard instrument with reliability coefficient of 0.81 was used to rate subjects in the six processing domains. Participants were sampled from primary one through primary six (mean age =10). Class teachers who served as Research Assistants were asked to rate the subjects in their respective classes by responding to items on CPI scale. Participants' consents were sought through their parents/guardians. Data obtained were analyzed using Percentage, Analysis of Variance and t-test at 95% confidence level. Results showed a high prevalence of 34.2% weakness in speed processing, 16.7% in auditory, 14.9% in conceptual and 12.5% in visual, whereas sequential and attention processing recorded 12.0% and 11.7% respectively. Similarly, ANOVA result ($F=4.123$ at $P<0.05$) reveals a significant difference in cognitive weakness among the six processing domains, while t-test analysis on gender difference in cognitive processing weakness was not significant ($t\text{-value}=0.23$; $P\text{-value}=0.981$). A recommendation offered suggests the use of cognitive rehabilitation and cognitive retraining as a measure to restore or strengthen cognitive functioning of the pupils.

Keywords: Cognitive Processing, Cognitive weakness, Primary school Pupils

Introduction

Primary school pupils exhibit differential abilities in mental processing. Such abilities occur in the six processing domains of the brain (Haruna, 2016). These domains are auditory, visual, sequential, conceptual, speed and attention or executive functioning (Crouse, 1999). Ability of the brain to effectively process information via these areas makes an individual to sense and perceive what goes around his/her environment. Naturally, there are individual differences in human cognitive functioning (Haruna, 2016) which may be caused by biological or environmental factors (Haruna, 2015). Persons whose brain structures and functions are not inhibited by any of the aforementioned factors tend to have strength in cognitive processing skills (Fiedorowicz, 1999), whereas those with inhibition in processing skills encounter some difficulties in perceptual processes, hence exhibit weakness in some or all of the processing domains (Crouse, 1999).

Several theories provide basis for the weakness in cognitive processing. Some of the theoretical frames that account for the problem include disturbance in information processing model of the brain (Plessis, 2001). Proponents of this view see the brain as information processing component, and that any disturbance in the processing model can impede learning. Another viewpoint is the intrinsic processing disorders (Hammill & Bryant, 1998). Proponents opine that certain intrinsic limitations or psychological processing dysfunction may be linked with pupil's inability to learn effectively (Hammill & Bryant, 1998). A neurobiological theory posits that weakness in cognitive processing is caused by subtle disturbances in the brain structures and functions, which may result in neurological dysfunction (Fiedorowicz, 1999). Another leading theory is that weakness in cognitive processing is genetically transmitted (Plomin, 2003). The theory postulates that, genes responsible for weakness in cognitive processing are the same genes responsible for normal variation in cognitive abilities.

The central point of view in the theories is recognition of abnormality in brain structures and functions, which is a significant requirement for learning. Given this background, it therefore means that pupils with weakness in cognitive processing may have an inherent difficulty to learn fast, recall what has been learnt, carry out arithmetic exercises, express thoughts through writing and adapt to school programme and activities (Crouse, 1999). These problems according to Crouse may show up as difficulty in understanding auditory information, visual information, memorize and organize facts in sequence, higher order thinking, speed in information processing and attention regulation.

Study by National Institutes of Health (2015) reveal that approximately 5% of school-age children have some type of auditory processing disorder. According to the Institutes, in children with learning difficulties the prevalence of auditory processing disorder has been found to be 43%. In addition, around 50% of children with dyslexia also have coexisting Auditory Processing Disorder (APD). Similar study by Haruna and Mayanchi (2013) on learning disabilities and its prevalence among secondary school students in Kano state, Nigeria found that 38.7% of the students had learning disabilities. Their findings also revealed prevalence of specific learning disabilities

among secondary school students as follows; listening 30.8%, speaking 25.8%, reading 14.7%, writing 9.2%, mathematics 9.5 and reasoning had 3.9%. Haruna (2015) in a separate report on gender difference in the prevalence of learning disabilities among secondary school students in Kano state showed no difference in prevalence between boys and girls. The significance of the findings by National Institutes of Health (2015), Haruna (2015) and Haruna and Mayanchi (2013) is that whereas cognitive processing weakness is considered as a major impediment to learning, it is also intrinsic to pupils with learning disabilities.

This phenomenon is not unusual among pupils in Demonstration Primary School (DPS), FCE Kano. With increase in school enrollment, teachers find it difficult to identify specific talents and skills of every pupil. Teaching strategies employed do not seem to cater for individual differences and sometimes can lead to frustration, failure, truancy and dropout (Haruna, 2016). Although several studies on specific processing disorders exist none has adequately addressed cognitive processing weakness of pupils in DPS. This study is therefore an attempt at bridging the gap. Thus two hypotheses tested in the study posit that:

1. There is no significant difference in weakness among the domains of cognitive processing.
2. There is no significant gender difference in cognitive processing weakness among pupils in DPS, Federal College of Education, Kano.

Research Methodology

The study covered all pupils in DPS, Federal College of Education, Kano whose population was 644 with a mean age of 10. Two hundred and thirty four participants were drawn following Research Advisors (2006) procedure for selecting sample size. Participants' consent was sought through the Head teacher who communicated to their parents/guardians. Pupil's cognitive status was however not a consideration for participation. To arrive at a representative sample, the proportion of each class level (stratum) was first determined as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Population and Sample size (N=644)

Class level	Population	Sample size	% of Sample
One	119	43	18.4
Two	118	43	18.4
Three	122	44	18.8
Four	127	46	19.6
Five	139	51	21.8
Six	19	07	3.0
Total	644	234	100

Field work, 2016

Guided by the statistics in table 1, random sampling was used to select participants from each stratum/class level. In order to ensure that every member of the population is given equal opportunity to participate in the study, serial numbers of pupils on class registers were copied on paper slips and blind folded. Thereafter the folded numbers were picked at random and corresponding names were selected to arrive at the required sample size for each class level. Since the study required a thorough understanding of cognitive behaviours of participants, six class teachers were engaged as Research Assistants. The Assistants were trained on the rudiments of the exercise, such as; random sampling, administration and scoring of data collection instrument etc.

The instrument used for data collection was a standardized scale called Cognitive Processing Inventory (CPI) designed by Crouse (1999). It consists of 50 items and each with likert response scales (1-5) at the right side of the protocol. Although CPI has an average internal consistency reliability coefficient of 0.87, the culture free test conducted using split-half reliability procedure reveals an average alpha coefficient of 0.80 for the scale. Research Assistants haven been trained on usage of the inventory, administered it on participants. A total of 250 CPI copies were given to the raters (Research Assistants) to enable them carry out the rating exercise. Extra copies of the inventory were also provided for rerating/replacement of damaged scale. In a nutshell, a period of four weeks was used for data collection and a total of 234 inventories were dully completed and returned.

Data obtained via the completed inventories were processed using CPI computer programme to determine cognitive statuses of participants. Frequency distribution and simple percentage were used for data description, while ANOVA and t-test statistics were applied to find out the difference in the prevalence of weakness among the processing domains as well as gender variation.

Results

Result of the diagnosis via CPI software is presented in table 2. The table presents frequency and percentage of weakness according to class level and gender across all the six areas of cognitive processing.

Table 2: Summary of rating of pupils with cognitive processing weakness (N=234)

Class	Auditory (n=39)		Visual (n=30)		Sequential (n=28)		Conceptual (n=35)		Speed (n=80)		Attention (n=27)	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
One	07	05	03	03	00	01	08	04	05	12	00	00
Two	04	02	01	00	02	02	07	04	04	07	03	02
Three	03	02	05	03	01	02	02	01	03	07	01	01
Four	02	01	02	01	03	03	03	02	04	07	04	02
Five	06	03	05	03	04	06	02	01	08	15	08	04
Six	02	01	02	02	02	02	00	01	03	05	01	01
Total	24	15	18	12	12	16	22	13	27	53	27	10
%	61.5	38.5	56.7	43.3	42.9	57.1	62.9	37.1	33.8	62.2	63.0	37.0

Field work, 2016

Statistics in table 2 show the frequency of weakness in the various cognitive processing domains among pupils in DPS. It illustrates that 39 cases of auditory weakness which constitutes 16.7% of auditory processing problem prevails among the pupils (male=61.5% and female=38.5%). Similarly, 12.8% (30 cases) of visual processing weakness exists (male=56.7% and female=43.3%), while sequential with 28 cases (male=42.9% and female=57.1%) and conceptual with 35 cases (male=62.9% and female=37.1%) have 12.0% and 14.9% respectively. Speed processing (34.2%) recorded the highest frequency of 80 cases of weakness (male=33.8% and female=62.2%). The domain with lowest frequency of weakness is attention processing (27 cases: male=63.0% and female=37.0%) whose prevalence stood at 11.3%.

H0 1

There is no significant difference in weakness among the domains of cognitive processing.

Table 3: ANOVA test showing difference in pupils' weakness in the cognitive domains

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig
Between group	339.8	5	67.96	4.123	0.05
Within group	494.5	30	16.48		
Total	834.3	35			

Field work, 2016

Statistics in table 3 reveal that the variability between group means is greater than average variability within group mean ($67.96 > 16.48$; $F=4.123$ at $P < 0.05$). This indicates that a significant difference in weakness exists among the six areas of cognitive processing. Thus null hypothesis one which supposes no difference in weakness is rejected.

H0 2

There is no significant gender difference in cognitive processing weakness among pupils in DPS, Federal College of Education, Kano.

Table 4: t-test analysis of gender difference in cognitive weakness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	SE	df	t-value	P-value	P<0.05
Male	6	19.83	5.49	2.24				
Female	6	20.0	16.30	6.65	10	0.023	0.981	Not Significant

Field work, 2016

The P-value of the calculation in table 4 (0.981) exceeds its t-value (0.023). This statistic is conventionally not significant at P<0.05 as such, the null hypothesis which supposes no gender difference is upheld.

Discussion on Findings

Result obtained from the analysis of data collected via CPI in respect to null hypothesis one reveals a significant difference in cognitive weakness among the six processing domains of cognitive processing. The analysis places speed processing (34.2%) as the domain with highest weakness and attention processing (11.7%) as the domain with the least weakness. This finding corroborates Haruna and Mayanchi (2013). In their study on learning disabilities and its prevalence among secondary school students, they adapted Learning Disabilities Diagnostic Inventory (LDDI) and rated 384 students sampled from 24 secondary schools in Kano state. Result of their study found a significant difference in prevalence of learning disabilities among the six areas of academic skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing, mathematics and reasoning). Haruna and Mayanchi’s result confirms the present one because weakness in cognitive processing is an attribute of learning disabilities (Crouse, 1999; and Hammill & Bryant, 1998).

Another finding from analysis of null hypothesis two reveals that boys and girls differ in their cognitive processing weakness. This finding is similar to the one by Haruna (2015) in his report on gender difference in prevalence of learning disabilities among secondary school students in Kano state. He reported that boys and girls do not differ. Also Giwa (1996) who investigated on learning problem in arithmetic among primary school pupils in Oyo Local Government Area found no significant gender difference in performance of children. Similarly, a study by Olanipeku (1996) on the effect of social skill programme on school achievement of children with moderate learning disabilities in primary schools in Nigeria showed a significant difference in pre-post test result among boys and girls. Although the present finding on gender difference in cognitive weakness deviates from that of Olanipekun (1996), the population of the studies (primary school pupils) are relatively similar.

Conclusion

Cognitive processing weakness is no doubt an intrinsic disorder that distorts learning process. The disorders are heterogenous in their prevalence among pupils in Demonstration Primary School, FCE Kano. Pupils in the school exhibit more weakness in speed and less problem in attention and executive functioning. Though boys and girls in the school do not significantly differ in their cognitive weakness, but the problem can have significant impact on learning progress of the pupils.

Recommendations

1. There should be retraining of teachers on the use of cognitive rehabilitation and cognitive retraining approaches in assisting pupils with weakness.
2. Male and female pupils should be properly diagnosed and adequately educated on their cognitive processing abilities and styles to enable them adapt to the environment and effectively manage their learning problems.

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